

Solvent Effect on the Emission Spectra of Anthracene Sulphonates and their Excited State Dipole Moments

SEKHAR BASU and K. K. ROHATGI-MUKHERJEE

Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700 032

Fluorescence and absorption spectra of anthracene-1-sulphonate (1-AS), anthracene-2-sulphonate (2-AS), anthracene-1,5-disulphonate (1,5-AS) and anthracene-1,8-disulphonate (1,8-AS) have been studied in a series of polar, protic and aprotic solvents. The ground state (μ_g) and excited state (μ_e) dipole moments were estimated according to approximate solvent shift theories for nonspecific interactions. The derived values so obtained are for μ_g 0.8, 5.8, 0.0 and 3.8 and for μ_e 4.4, 6.7, 0.0 and 6.7 for 1-AS, 2-AS, 1,5-AS and 1,8-AS, respectively. Intramolecular charge transfer from π -electronic ring system of anthracene moiety to the SO_3^- group can explain large increase in dipole moment on excitation for 1-AS, 2-AS and 1,8-AS and $\Delta\mu=0$ for 1,5-AS of symmetry C_{2v} . The diffuse nature of fluorescence only for 1-AS in water has been ascribed to exciplex formation. The higher $\Delta\mu$ value of 1-AS is indicative of rather more polar excited state than other compounds and its low symmetry (C_2) promotes exciplex formation.

THE nature and polarity of a solvent do not have large effect on the absorption and emission spectra of anthracene¹⁻³, but polar solvent-induced loss in vibrational structure and pronounced red shift of fluorescence spectra for substituted anthracenes⁴⁻⁵ have been a subject of many investigations and discussions. The presence of highly polar groups in the anthracene ring enhances dipole-dipole interaction with the solvent. Veljkovic¹ suggested an additional kind of interaction between π -electrons of the excited anthracene molecule and p-electrons of the solvent molecules. On the other hand Werner⁴ established that the large Stokes' shift of 9-methyl anthroate in protic solvents could be due to contribution of hydrogen bond in the excited state.

For 9-anthroic acid Werner *et al*³⁻⁵ observed that the absorption spectrum retains its anthracene like structure while the fluorescence spectrum becomes diffuse and highly red shifted. These observations have been attributed by them to the differences in the ground and excited state geometries of the molecule. Due to steric hindrance, the $-\text{COOH}$ group or its ester at 9-position maintains a perpendicular position to the plane of the anthracene moiety. Since the substituent cannot conjugate in this geometry, the characteristics of the parent molecule are retained in the absorption spectrum. In the excited state, a coplanar geometry is achieved and there arises a possibility of a number of conformers as a function of angle θ between the plane of the $-\text{COOMe}$ group and the anthracene skeleton. As a result, the fluorescence spectra are broad and diffuse. The spectra of 1- and 2-substituted compounds were also explained by assuming changes in geometry on excitation, and the effect of solvent on the first excited state S_1 . From the effects of solvent polarity and its aprotic or protic nature on fluorescence and absorption maxima and using the equation of Lippert⁶, an increase of 4.5 D for the excited state dipole moment of 9-methyl anthroate has been calculated. Furthermore from the steady state as

well as from time resolved fluorescence spectroscopy for 1- and 2-acetyl and benzoyl anthracenes, Tamaki⁷ demonstrated that the perturbation of fluorescence spectra by protic solvents is caused by a combination of the orientational dipolar solvent-solute relaxation and the hydrogen bond interaction.

Mataga and co-workers^{2,8} interpreted the red shift for indole and its derivatives in terms of a generalized dipole-dipole interaction between solute and solvent in the excited state. The red shift is due to large increase of dipole moment on excitation and thus a greater solute-solvent stabilization in the fluorescent state as compared to the ground and Frank-Condon (FC) excited state. For *p*-dimethyl aminobenzonitrile Lippert⁹ proposed a reversal of 1L_a and 1L_b states during the life time of the excited state in polar solvents as an explanation for the relatively large Stokes' shift. Walker¹⁰ suggested a specific solute-solvent excited state complex (exciplex) for indole in polar solvents.

It has already been reported^{11,12} that anthracene sulphonates exhibit variation in their excited state properties i.e. fluorescence spectral nature, radiative life time, fluorescence quantum yields, etc. depending upon the number and position of the sulphonate (SO_3^-) groups introduced in the anthracene moiety. In aqueous solution, anthracene-1-sulphonate (1-AS) gives structureless and anthracene-2-sulphonate (2-AS) gives nearly structureless fluorescence spectra. On the other hand, fluorescence spectra for anthracene-1,5-disulphonate (1,5-AS) and anthracene-1,8-disulphonate (1,8-AS) have vibrational features, and the mirror image symmetry relationship between absorption and emission spectra is preserved. In aprotic solvents the vibrational fine structures in the emission spectrum of mono sulphonates are restored, the spectrum shifts towards blue and the quantum yield of fluorescence is reduced. Such differences in the excited state properties have been considered here in the light of the following known arguments: i) increase

in excited state dipole moment, ii) intramolecular or intermolecular hydrogen bonding, iii) exciplex formation, iv) changes in excited state geometry of the molecule and v) reversal of energy levels of fluorescence states. It may be noted that the SO₃⁻ group has been considered to be noninteracting in the ground as well as in the excited state in contrast to carboxylic acids, their esters or the carbonyl groups. The ground and excited state dipole moments of these sulphonates have been estimated according to approximate solvent shift theories for nonspecific interactions.

Experimental

Anthracene 1- and 2-monosulphonates and 1,5- and 1,8-disulphonates, abbreviated as 1-AS, 2-AS, 1,5-AS and 1,8-AS, were prepared from corresponding quinones by the method described earlier¹³. The solvents used were spectroscopic or G. R. grade reagents. Formamide (FMD), glycerol (GLY), ethylene glycol (EG), acetonitrile (ACN), ethyl alcohol (EtOH) and tetrahydrofuran (THF) were dried by standard procedures and purified by fractional distillation. Emission impurities were checked.

Absorption spectra were measured manually by Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, Model Hitachi 200. The fluorescence spectra were recorded with a Perkin Elmer MPF 44B spectrofluorimeter.

The shift in O-O transition due to solvent interaction in the ground and excited states of the molecule can be explained with the help of Franck Condon principle for absorption and emission process. Several authors have correlated the solvent polarity parameter involving dielectric constant, D, and refractive index, n, with Stokes' shift. Within zeroth order approximations solute-solvent interactions are primarily of dipole-dipole nature including dispersion force interactions. The short range interaction such as hydrogen bonding is neglected in these equations. For determination of ground and excited state dipole moments of anthracene sulphonates, modified method of Pill-Soon-Song¹⁴ was followed. This method is based on three formulae derived to interpret Stokes' shift and characteristic properties of the solvents.

(i) According to Lippert⁶ and Kawski¹⁵

$$\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f = \frac{2\Delta\mu^2}{\bar{a}^3 hc} F_1 \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\text{where } F_1 = \frac{2(D-1)}{2D+1} - \frac{2(n^2-1)}{2n^2+1} \quad \dots (2)$$

$\bar{\nu}_a$ and $\bar{\nu}_f$ are O-O absorption and emission frequencies in cm⁻¹, respectively, $\Delta\mu^2 = (\mu_a - \mu_g)^2$ where μ_g and μ_a are permanent dipole moments in ground and excited emitting states, h is the Planck constant, c is the speed of light in vacuum and \bar{a} is the Onsager cavity radius assuming solvent to be a medium of continuous dielectric. For anthracene sulphonates \bar{a} can be estimated from the size of the molecule. Here it was calculated from the density measurements.

(ii) The formula due to Bakhshiev¹⁶ is as given below :

$$\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f = \frac{2\Delta\mu^2}{\bar{a}^3 hc} F_2 \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\text{where } F_2 = \frac{2n^2+1}{n^2+2} \left(\frac{D-1}{D+2} - \frac{n^2-1}{n^2+2} \right) \quad \dots (4)$$

and $\Delta\mu^2 \approx (\mu_a^2 - \mu_g^2)$

(iii) The Chamma-Viallet¹⁷ formula is

$$\frac{\bar{\nu}_a + \bar{\nu}_f}{2} = -\frac{2\Delta\mu^2}{\bar{a}^3 hc} F_3 \quad \dots (5)$$

$$\text{where } F_3 = \frac{1}{2}F_2 + \frac{(n^2-1)}{(n^2+2)^2} \quad \dots (6)$$

and $\Delta\mu^2 = (\mu_a^2 - \mu_g^2)$

F₁, F₂ and F₃ terms are functions of solvent polarity. The Stokes' shift $\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f$ or $(\bar{\nu}_a + \bar{\nu}_f)/2$ in a series of solvents have been plotted according to the equations (1), (3) and (5), yielding slopes which are determined by the size of $\Delta\mu$. Since the solvent dielectric constants and refractive index terms are known, the solvent functions F₁, F₂ and F₃ can be calculated directly, and are presented in Table 1. As some of the spectra for monosulphonates in polar and protic solvents are diffuse in

TABLE 1—CALCULATED VALUES OF SOLVENT FUNCTIONS

Solvent	D at 25°	n at 25°	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃
Formamide	109.50	1.4461	0.5652	0.8949	0.7497
Water	78.54	1.3330	0.6398	0.9128	0.6833
Glycerol	42.50	1.4173	0.5630	0.8523	0.7095
Ethylene glycol	40.70	1.4290	0.5537	0.8452	0.7136
Acetonitrile	35.95	1.3420	0.6107	0.8599	0.6628
Ethyl alcohol	24.55	1.3590	0.5792	0.8136	0.6512
Tetrahydrofuran	7.58	1.4040	0.4213	0.5505	0.5497

nature, the difference between the absorption and emission maxima in different solvents have been used for the calculation of Stokes' shift. The corresponding solvent shift data for AS are presented in Table 2. The sample concentration was of the order of 5 × 10⁻⁶ M in all the cases. The Stokes' shift in a series of solvent is plotted against F₁, F₂ and F₃ terms upto a first order approximations, in Figs. 1-3. The slopes S₁, S₂ and S₃ and intercepts of the plots were obtained by least square method (Table 3).

The excited state dipole moments (μ_e) were obtained by combining equations (3) and (5) giving equation (7),

$$\mu_e = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\bar{a}^3 hc S_3}{2} \right)^{1/2} \left(1 - \frac{S_2}{S_3} \right) \quad \dots (7)$$

$\Delta\mu$ values and from there the ground state dipole moments (μ_g) were obtained from the equation (1) because it gave straight lines of good correlation coefficient. The calculated values of dipole moments are presented in Table 4.

TABLE 2—SOLVENT SHIFT DATA FOR ANTHRACENE SULPHONATES

Solvent	1-AS		2-AS		1,5-AS		1,8-AS	
	ν_{α}^{max} (cm ⁻¹)	ν_{β}^{max} (cm ⁻¹)	ν_{α}^{max} (cm ⁻¹)	ν_{β}^{max} (cm ⁻¹)	ν_{α}^{max} (cm ⁻¹)	ν_{β}^{max} (cm ⁻¹)	ν_{α}^{max} (cm ⁻¹)	ν_{β}^{max} (cm ⁻¹)
FMD	27397	23917	27777	23747	27247	24177	27100	23700
H ₂ O	27548	23810	27777	23977	27472	24362	27173	23753
GLY	27247	23866	27624	24096	27100	24038	26954	23810
EG	27472	23882	27700	23940	27322	24222	27173	23923
ACN	27700	24290	28011	24331	27397	24267	27173	23953
EtOH	27624	24274	27855	24235	27322	24272	27247	23967
THF	27625	24394	28089	24469	27322	24212	27397	24297

TABLE 3—CALCULATED SLOPES OF EQUATIONS 1, 3 AND 5

Compound	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃
1-AS	1255	444	-1705
2-AS	768	354	-2529
1,5-AS	0	0	0
1,8-AS	1485	456	-2406

Fig. 1. Stokes' shift of anthracene sulphonates plotted against solvent function F₁.

Fig. 2. Stokes' shift of anthracene sulphonates plotted against solvent function F₂.

Fig. 3. Approximate O-O frequencies of anthracene sulphonates plotted against solvent function F₃.

Results and Discussion

Dipole moment

Anthracene has three positions for mono sulphonation and the ability of the SO₃⁻ group to interact electronically with the anthracene ring is quite dependent on the position of substitution. The 9-position of anthracene ring is the most electron rich

TABLE 4—DIPOLE MOMENTS IN THE GROUND AND EXCITED STATE OF ANTHRACENE SULPHONATES

Compound	(in Debye units)		
	Δμ D	μ _g D	μ _e D
1-AS	3.6	0.8 ± 0.2	4.4 ± 0.2
2-AS	0.9	5.8 ± 0.1	6.7 ± 0.1
1,5-AS	0.0	0.0	0.0
1,8-AS	2.9	3.8 ± 0.1	6.7 ± 0.1

position and the 2-position is the least electron rich. The electron density at the 1-position is intermediate between the other two positions. The ground state energy of these sulphonates are not much affected on sulphonation because the -SO₃⁻ group interacts only to a small extent¹⁸. In the excited state the SO₃⁻ group appears to have considerable interaction with the anthracene ring. Izawa *et al*¹⁹ studied the photolysis of sodium 9-anthracene sulphonate. 9-10-Anthaquinone was obtained via 9-anthrol anion by desulfonylation (-SO₃⁻) brought about

by $n-\pi^*$ transition, and anthracene by desulphonation ($-\text{SO}_3^-$) by $\pi-\pi^*$ transition. The most important process in the desulphonylation considered by them was an intramolecular rearrangement to give oxathian ring in the $n-\pi^*$ state. Presumably an $n-\pi^*$ state is provided by the SO_3^- group very near to $\pi-\pi^*$ state.

The interaction of SO_3^- group is prominent for anthracene sulphonates in the excited state since ν_{max} in inactive solvent like acetonitrile is shifted to about 590 cm^{-1} for all sulphonates relative to anthracene. The interaction with polar solvents also increases on excitation. The large increase of dipole moment on excitation for these compounds can be due to flow of charge from the π -electron ring system of the anthracene moiety to the SO_3^- group. SO_3^- group is an electron withdrawing group. This intramolecular charge transfer can explain $\Delta\mu=0$ for 1,5-AS. The dipole direction appears to be along the short axis of the molecule. The greater the electron withdrawing ability of the substituent the greater is the dipole moment and greater the shift of fluorescence maximum to the longer wavelength. The dipole moment values of 1- and 2-acylanthracenes⁷ show similar behaviour. The 1,5-AS with centre of symmetry behaves similar to anthracene. On the other hand 1,8-AS develops a high dipole moment both in the ground and the excited state, compared to 1-AS. The greater expression of dipole moment for 2-AS in the ground state (5.8 D) and the excited state (6.7 D), as compared to 1-AS, can arise out of the attachment of electron withdrawing SO_3^- group to the 2-position of the ring, which is the least electron rich position, and consequent large contributions from the electronic configuration of the type II. The large $\Delta\mu$ (3.6 D) values of 1-AS is indicative of rather more polar excited state than other sulphonates. By comparison, Mataga *et al.*⁸ found $\mu_e - \mu_g$ to be 0.5–1.0 D for β -naphthyl methyl ether and α,β -naphthol, while Seliskar and Brand^{9,10} observed the difference to be 9 D for 2-amino-6-naphthalene sulphonate.

Hydrogen bonding :

Besides the dipolar effects, significant hydrogen bonding interaction may contribute to Stokes' shift in protic solvents which can explain the structureless emission of 1-AS and slightly structured emission for 2-AS. Tamaki⁷ reported red shifts for 1- and 2-acylanthracene in protic solvents and assumed the formation of hydrogen bond. They observed a stabilization energy of the order of 1500 cm^{-1} in these systems and 1800 cm^{-1} is reported for indole¹¹. Similar observation is reported for

methyl anthracene carboxylate⁸. The hydrogen bond formation is facilitated due to increased basicity of $-\text{CO}$ group as a consequence of preferential migration of electronic charge on photoexcitation.

The solution of 1-AS in acetonitrile gives structured emission even when it is perturbed by a very small amount of water or added alcohol (0.01M) which otherwise is insufficient to alter the absorption spectrum or the dielectric properties of the solvent. The fluorescence spectrum also does not change or shift to any considerable extent. Furthermore, difference in the solvent shift data for emission spectra of 1-AS and 2-AS in MeOH as compared to those in ACN are only 118 and 179 cm^{-1} respectively. The two solvents are isodielectric but differ in their H-bonding capacity. The shifts are too small to explain stabilization by hydrogen bond formation. Finally, the fluorescence spectra of anthracene sulphonates are not affected by pH changes or high acidity except for a red-shift of 480 cm^{-1} for mono-sulphonate solutions between 1N and 2N HCl. All the above observations do not support specific hydrogen bonding in polar system or possibility of internal or external proton transfer in the excited state. The red shift for some sulphonates follows the common polarity scale of Kosower which represents the microscopic dielectric constant (z value) of the solvents. The interaction with the solvent seems to be rather of collective type. Solvent structure definitely has important part to play. Such interaction is accompanied by activation of fluorescence rather than quenching for monosulphonates in protic solvents. Förster and Rokos^{12,13} observed decrease in the fluorescence quantum yield, ϕ_{fl} , with anomalous Stoke's shift for N,N-dimethyl-1-amino-5-naphthalene sulphonate in water in contrast to inactive solvents like dimethylformamide.

Exciplex formation

The solvent shift data of 1-AS in water deviates significantly from the linear relationship between Stokes' shift and solvent functions F_1 , F_2 and F_3 in Figs. 1-3. Such deviation is not prominent for other sulphonates. It is thus clear that specific interaction between the solute and the solvent molecules is playing an important role in large Stokes' shift for 1-AS in polar solvents, particularly in water. The widely accepted mechanism for such specific interaction is exciplex formation, proposed by Walker *et al.*¹⁴ for indoles and confirmed by others¹⁴⁻¹⁶.

In general, exciplexes and excimers are known to have structureless and broad spectra with ν_{max} shifted to lower frequency. Thus it appears that in the case of monosulphonates, specially for 1-AS, a weak exciplex i.e. a dipole-dipole stabilized complex, is formed between excited sulphonate molecule and a number of polar water molecules.

There are several possible reasons why 1,5-AS and 1,8-AS do not form exciplex with water. For 1,5-AS, its zero dipole moment both in ground and excited states is not conducive to exciplex formation.

On the other hand for 1,8-AS although the excited state dipole moment is fairly large ($\mu_e = 6.7$ D) the molecule possesses considerable symmetry (C_{2v}). Very low symmetry of monosulphonates is an important factor promoting exciplex formation in 1-AS. The observed life time^{1,2} values for the sulphonates further support the exciplex mechanism. For 1-AS, the calculated life time in H₂O by Strickler-Berg expression is quite small (3.4 ns) as compared to that obtained from single photon counting technique (7.3 ns). It has been already reported^{2,7} that ¹L_a is the emitting state for all the AS in all the solvents and not the ¹L_b, and there is no question of reversal of energy levels of fluorescence state of 1-AS in H₂O. It may be concluded that the molecular symmetry and geometry are important considerations for treatment of generalised solute-solvent interactions.

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge financial assistance of the University Grants Commission, New Delhi and a maintenance grant to one of them (S. B.).

References

1. S. R. VELJKOVIC, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, 53, 1181.
2. N. MATAGA, Y. KAIFU and M. KOIZUMI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1956, 29, 465.
3. T. C. WERNER and R. N. HOFFAMAN, *J. Phy. Chem.*, 1973, 77, 1611.
4. T. C. WERNER and D. M. HERCULES, *J. Phy. Chem.*, 1969, 73, 2005.
5. T. C. WERNER, T. MATTEWS and B. SOLLER, *J. Phy. Chem.*, 1976, 80, 533.
6. E. LIPPERT, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1955, 10a, 541; *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1957, 61, 962.
7. T. TAMAKI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1980, 53, 577; 1978, 51, 2817.
8. N. MATAGA, V. TORIHASHI and K. EZUMI, *Theo. Chim. Acta*, 1964, 2, 158.
9. E. LIPPERT, *Adv. Mol. Spectry.*, 1962, 1, 443.
10. M. S. WALKER, T. W. BEDNAR and R. W. LUMRY, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1967, 47, 1020; 1966, 45, 3455.
11. K. K. ROHATGI-MUKHERJEE and B. P. SINGH, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1971, 75, 595.
12. A. K. GUPTA, S. BASU and K. K. ROHATGI-MUKHERJEE, *Cand. J. Chem.*, 1980, 58, 1046.
13. A. K. GUPTA, B. P. SINGH and K. K. ROHATGI-MUKHERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 382.
14. M. SUN and P. S. SONG, *Photochem. Photobiol.*, 1977, 25, 3.
15. V. A. KAWSKI, *Acta Phys. Polon.*, 1966, 29, 507.
16. N. G. BAKHSHIEV, *Opt. Spektrosk.*, 1964, 61, 821.
17. A. CHAMMA and P. VIALLET, *C. R. Acad. Sci. Ser.*, 1970, C270, 1901.
18. A. BRYSON, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1951 47, 528.
19. Y. IZAWA, N. SUZUKI, A. INOUE and ITO, *J. C. S. Chem. Comm.*, 1976, 24, 1048.
20. C. SELISKAR and L. BRAND, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 93, 5414.
21. E. V. DONCKT, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belges.*, 1969, 78, 69.
22. TH. FORSTER and K. ROKOS, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1967, 1, 279.
23. M. S. WALKER, T. W. BEDNAR, R. LUMRY and F. HUMPHRY, *Photochem. Photobiol.*, 1971, 14, 147.
24. J. A. IBEMESI and M. A. EL-BAYOUMI, *Photochem. Photobiol.*, 1980, 31, 97.
25. J. W. LONGWORTH and M. D. C. BATTISTA, *Photochem. Photobiol.*, 1970, 12, 29.
26. O. S. KHALIL, H. HOFER and S. P. MCGLYNN, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1972, 17, 479.
27. S. BASU and K. K. ROHATGI-MUKHERJEE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1983, 22A, 186.